

A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND SYSTEMATIC DIFFERENTIATION OF ENGINEERING VERIFICATION APPROACHES IN FIRE SAFETY, BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF THE GERMAN STANDARD

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Abstract

This paper presents a theoretical analysis and systematic differentiation of engineering verification types in fire safety engineering, beginning with the principles outlined in the German Standard. This Standard delineates two verification categories: argumentative engineering verification and performance-based verification. Each of them is based on identifying fire scenarios. Argumentative verification involves presenting causal relationships that show the fulfillment of functional requirements through logical reasoning, expert judgment, and qualitative evidence. Performance-based verification utilizes calculation models to demonstrate adherence to predefined or derived performance criteria, which determine an acceptable level of incident damage. This method allows for the evaluation of fire protection measures based on their effectiveness in preventing or mitigating such incidents. Alongside the two engineering approaches, this paper describes a third, risk-based engineering approach. It outlines the necessary steps to develop a qualified risk-based method for demonstrating compliance in fire safety engineering.

1 Introduction

Fire safety planning in Germany is primarily based on prescriptive rules. Complex buildings and new construction methods often exceed the limits of these regulations, requiring specific assessment by fire safety engineering. Demonstrating compliance with safety objectives is the central task of such evaluations.

The development of technical rules and standards accompanies the adoption of engineering-based evidence in the practice of fire safety engineering. This promotes the acceptance of plans that are developed and technically validated using engineering methods. In this context, DIN is developing a series of standards for fire safety engineering, which also allows for the integration of international fire safety standards.

With the publication of the first part of this standard in 2016 [2], which governs principles and procedures for its application, Germany took an initial step toward overall formal acceptance of performance-based evidence. Besides its specific application for life safety and evacuation simulations [4, 5], covered in the second part of the standard [3], additional parts are currently being developed to establish and hopefully integrate these into German building regulations. In particular, the systematic treatment of variations and uncertainties is to be addressed in another standard part covering safety concepts. This motivates the systematic consideration of the two engineering verification categories outlined in the German Standard: argumentative and performance-based, both of which are grounded in a shared foundation — the explicit definition of fire scenarios and functional requirements. The latter are specifically derived from the fire safety objectives and are accordingly assigned to them [6]. This structure appears to be consistent with the computational tools and model capabilities commonly applied in engineering practice.

However, the discipline evolved around simulation models that primarily resolve physical phenomena (e.g., heat release, smoke movement, tenability, and egress dynamics). These models do not provide "damage" as an output, whether measured in terms of casualties, economic loss, functional downtime, or environmental impact. As a result, while it is feasible to demonstrate that limit states, defined through performance criteria, are unlikely to be exceeded for a set of scenarios, it is not possible to calculate risk as a product of probability and damage.

This theoretical review clarifies the foundations of the established verification categories, articulates their limitations, but also their necessity for developing conceptual contours for a risk-based approach.

2 Methodology

2.1 Principal verification types defined by the German Standard

The German standard clearly outlines two distinct categories of engineering verification: argumentative engineering verification and performance-based verification. Each type requires the selection of fire scenarios and the formulation of specific functional requirements

Figure 1: Overview of consecutive steps to apply fire safety engineering

derived from well-established fire safety objectives. An overview of the consecutive steps, as outlined in the German Standard, is presented in Figure 1.

1. Argumentative engineering verification involves assessing a trial design through logical reasoning and analysis. This process often incorporates estimation methods, including the application of engineering judgment and expertise. The objective is to achieve immediate acceptance of the fire safety measures based on well-founded arguments or scientific findings as qualitative evidence. The standard defines a specific approach for outlining an argument.
2. Performance-based verification has developed around physical and behavioral models, including zone and field (Computational Fluid Dynamics, or CFD) fire models, structural responses to fire, and evacuation simulations.

For the application of performance-based verification, the standard requires the specification of performance criteria related to the functional requirements, which consist of a physical quantity with an associated threshold value, and thereby define the limit state. The physical quantity of the performance criteria must be predictable based on the underlying model applied.

However, the scope of applied models is limited to physical and behavioral responses; they do not provide information on casualties, monetary loss, downtime, or environmental impact. As a result, practitioners can offer pass or fail evidence with respect to the limit state but will neither reach a risk value nor determine a risk-optimized solution. This creates a gap, as the standard promotes a risk-oriented selection of scenarios for fire safety engineering verification. The estimated damage consequences for the scenario selection cannot be predicted a posteriori due to a lack of information about the outcomes.

2.2 Differentiation of engineering verification approaches regarding uncertainties and safety concepts

In this part of the analysis, it is demonstrated that three different approaches can be considered for managing uncertainties as safety concepts: conservative assumptions, parameter studies and sensitivity analyses, and probabilistic analysis. Furthermore, it is systematically

Figure 2: Overview of verification types connected to safety concepts and output

questioned to what extent the application of the safety concept is decisive for the categorization into the respective verification category. The connection between verification types and safety concepts is shown in Figure 2

1. *Conservative assumptions*

The treatment of uncertainties and the underlying safety concepts vary significantly across the three engineering verification approaches. In the case of argumentative verification, the most widely recognized and practically applicable safety concept is the use of conservative assumptions to maintain a "safe-side" position. This approach relies on addressing uncertainty implicitly by adopting worst-case or highly cautious input values.

2. *Parameter studies and sensitivity analysis*

In contrast, performance-based verification depends on computational models and scenario analyses. Here, uncertainties cannot be fully captured by a single deterministic calculation. If only one calculation is performed, it serves merely as an illustrative example and ultimately functions as an argument within an argumentative framework. To achieve a robust performance-based verification, parameter studies and sensitivity analyses are essential. These allow the identification of influential variables and provide insight into the variability of outcomes under different plausible conditions.

3. Probabilistic analysis

When input parameters are represented by their statistical distributions in a probabilistic analysis, the safety level can be quantified explicitly. This allows for the calculation of the probability that specified limit states will not be exceeded, providing a clear measure of reliability. This probabilistic approach forms the foundation for risk-based methodologies, where probabilities are used to derive risk metrics considering the potential outcome damage.

2.3 Description of an additional risk-based engineering approach

Risk-based verification extends beyond demonstrating compliance with predefined performance criteria by explicitly evaluating safety measures in relation to the expected risk.

As a first step, risk can be defined by examining a specific scenario, particularly for the design scenario. In this context, the risk of the particular scenario can be considered as the product of the scenario's occurrence probability, P_s , and the expected amount of damage D_s . Calculating that value could help bridge the earlier-mentioned gap, considering the risk-oriented scenario selection within a performance-based approach.

This still does not address risk-based verification, as other scenarios are also possible to occur. So the overall risk for a given design must be considered as the probability-weighted consequence across a comprehensive set of scenarios:

$$\text{Risk} = \sum P(s) D(s), \quad (1)$$

where $P(s)$ denotes the probability of scenario s and $D(s)$ denotes the damage or consequence [1].

Required Components and steps towards a risk-based method:

1. *Integration of Probability and Consequence*: jointly considering the likelihood of fire scenarios and the magnitude of damage (fatalities/injuries, monetary loss, downtime, environmental impact).
2. *Scenario modeling*: a systematic, sufficiently complete set of scenarios with assigned probabilities.
3. *Damage modeling*: functions that translate physical outputs into consequences (expected fatalities, monetary loss, downtime).
4. *Risk aggregation*: computation of expected risk across scenarios, optionally with risk profiles or FN-curves [6].
5. *Acceptance criteria*: explicit thresholds for individual and societal risk, ALARP-style criteria, or cost-benefit-based benchmarks.

The missing damage modeling is a significant current limitation. Actual simulation models do not directly output damage metrics, and without a damage function, expected risk cannot be computed. However, when enabled by credible damage models and acceptance criteria, risk-based verification provides a quantitative basis for safety decisions. It allows performance optimization, rather than merely passing or failing verification.

3 Conclusion

Today's technical standards for addressing fire safety engineering tasks include argumentative engineering verification and performance-based verification, particularly when prescriptive measures are not applicable.

When probabilistic safety concepts are applied in performance-based verifications, the probability of reaching the respective limit state can be quantified. However, quantifying the risk requires an assessment of the expected damage. Further research is necessary to establish models and scales for damage assessment. This has the potential to bridge the gap in risk-oriented scenario selection for performance-based design.

Established models are crucial for comprehending fire phenomena and developing effective fire safety measures. Their application in fire safety engineering practice enables alternatives to prescriptive solutions. Those models also form the basis for developing risk-based verification strategies, as their results are likely essential for consequence analysis and damage assessment.

References

- [1] Gianluca De Sanctis. *Generic Risk Assessment for Fire Safety: Performance Evaluation and Optimisation of Design Provisions: Performance Evaluation and Optimisation of Design Provisions*. IBK Bericht 363. ETH Zurich, Oct. 2015, 174 p. DOI: 10.3929/ETHZ-A-010562998.
- [2] DIN 18009-1. *Brandschutzingenieurwesen – Teil 1: Grundsätze und Regeln für die Anwendung*. Deutsche Norm. Berlin, Sept. 2016.
- [3] DIN 18009-2. *Brandschutzingenieurwesen – Teil 2: Räumungssimulation und Personensicherheit*. Deutsche Norm. Berlin, Aug. 2022.
- [4] Gregor Jäger and Benjamin Schröder. “Evacuation and Life Safety Assessment in Germany.” In: *Proceedings of 11th Conference on Performance-Based Codes and Fire Safety Design Methods*. Conference on Performance-Based Codes and Fire Safety Design Methods. Ed. by Piotr Tofilo. Warsaw: Society of Fire Protection Engineers (SFPE), 2016, pp. 37–50. ISBN: 978-83-938077-5-8.
- [5] Manuel Kitzlinger, Benjamin Schröder, and Gregor Jäger. “Räumungssimulation und Personenstromberechnungen nach DIN 18009-2.” In: *Bauphysik-Kalender 2025*. Berlin: Ernst & Sohn, 2025, pp. 357–394. ISBN: 978-3-433-61209-5. DOI: 10.1002/9783433612095.ch10.
- [6] Björn Maiworm, Claudius Hammann, and Michael Schleich. “Prescriptive Building Regulations, Safety Objectives, and Residual Risk in Germany.” In: *Fire Technology* 59.6 (July 18, 2023), pp. 3203–3230. ISSN: 0015-2684, 1572-8099. DOI: 10.1007/s10694-023-01456-x.